

EVALUATION OF PRODUCTIVITY AND PRODUCTIVITY COMPOUNDS IN TOMATO ACCESSIONS GROWN UNDER ELEVATED TEMPERATURE AND REDUCED IRRIGATION

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Abstract

The aim of this experimental work was to evaluate the productivity and productivity compounds in tomato accessions grown under elevated temperature and reduced irrigation. The experiment was conducted at the Maritsa Vegetable Crops Research Institute with 25 tomato accessions (14 determinate and 11 indeterminate) in the period of 2016 and 2017. Two watering regimes were applied - optimum and 50% reduced. Productivity per plant, number of fruits per plant and average fruit weight were measured. Environmental descriptors air temperature, air humidity, rainfalls and soil moisture at 15 and 30 cm depth were recorded by weather station Caipos Wave. As a result of reduced irrigation and high temperatures a decrease of the productivity per plant formed on the base of number and average fruit weight was observed. The studied indeterminate tomato accessions showed low heat tolerance compared to the determinate ones. Decrease of the productivity per plant with 25.2% close to the positive control was established in accession BG 985 from the determinate tomato for processing and with 35.5% in accession Spectar belonging to the determinate tomato for fresh consumption. A decrease of the productivity less than 50% was observed only in indeterminate tomato accession BG 21β (47.3%). The reduced irrigation and the high temperatures had a weaker negative effect on the fruit number (13.3-57.1%) and average fruit weight per plant (5.0-57.8%) compared to the productivity. Three-way analysis of variance showed that watering regime influenced mainly the productivity per plant in the three studied tomato groups, fruit number and average fruit weight per plant in determinate tomato for fresh consumption. Differences in number and average fruit weight per plant in determinate tomato for processing and indeterminate ones were determined by genotype. As a result of this study perspective tomato accessions suitable for breeding of drought stress were selected.

Key words: *Solanum lycopersicum, high temperature, drought, fruit set*

1. INTRODUCTION

Climatic changes associated with the increase of air temperature and drought are among the most important factors that limit productivity and quality in horticultural crops (Fahad et al. 2015). In tomato high temperature stress leads to flower abortion, limited fruit set and weight (Abdelmageed & Gruda 2009; Xu et al. 2017). In addition, elevated temperature is also reflected in quality of tomato fruits, sensory evaluation and nutrition value (Ansary 2006; Hernandez et al. 2015; Agbemafle, Owusu-Sekyere & Bart-Plange 2015). Peet, Wentworth & White (1998) demonstrated that fruit number, fruit weight and seed per plant in tomato decreased as main daily temperature rose above 25°C and was severely impaired at 29°C. According to Hazara et al. (2007) such moderately elevated temperature stress does not affect normal plant growth and reduction of fruit formation in these conditions is due probably to different reproductive malfunctioning. In temperature stress significant changes were observed in flower morphology, pollen production and fertility, abnormal development of the female reproductive tissues, hormonal imbalances, low levels of carbohydrates, lack of pollination and flower but abortion (Pressman, Peet & Phar 2002; Camejo et al. 2005; Harel et al. 2014).

Water deficit resulting from insufficient rainfalls or deficient soil moisture is another stress factor which affects negatively plant growth and productivity (Boutraa 2010; Nahar & Ullah 2011). It was established that irrigation at the reduced rate to 50% led to significant decrease of fruit number, fruit diameter, fruit weight and yield in tomato (Patanè, Tringali & Sortino 2011; Sivakumar & Srividhya 2016). Lovelli et al. (2017) obtained 37% reduce of total yield when half of the crop evapotranspiration was restored. On the other hand Zhou et al. (2017) observed similar physiological responses, limited plant growth,

photosynthesis and chlorophyll fluorescence in drought, combined drought-heat stress and concluded that the effect on tomato fruit setting and yield would need further studies.

Significant progress has been achieved for understanding the physiological, biochemical and genetic basis of high temperature and drought tolerance in tomato (Faruq et al. 2012; Solankey et al. 2015; Bhattarai et al. 2016) but the experiments of breeding in field conditions during summer season with measurement of fruit set and yield are still limited. According to EL-Saka (2016) screening and selection of tomato genotypes tolerant to abiotic stresses should be conducted to vegetative and fruited stage.

This study evaluated the effect of elevated temperature and reduced irrigation on productivity and productivity compounds of Bulgarian tomato accessions for fresh consumption and processing with the aim to identify genotypes tolerant to applied stress for including them into a future breeding program.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Materials

The field experiments were conducted in two consecutive years (2016 and 2017) at the Maritsa Vegetable Crops Research Institute in Plovdiv. Twenty five tomato accessions were included in this study. The accessions were divided into three groups: determinate for processing (Kapri, Neven, Pautalia – semi-determinate, Venera, BG 160, BG 1527, BG 2086 and BG 985), determinate for fresh consumption (Marti, Milyana, Solaris, Spectar and BG 252), indeterminate for fresh consumption (Aleno sartse, Ideal, Plovdivska karotina, Rozovo sartse, BG 21 β , BG 24/13, BG 720, BG 735, BG 785, BG 822, and BG 2066) and positive control JAG 8810.

2.2. Experimental design

The seeds of selected accessions were sown at the beginning of April in unheated greenhouse. The tomato seedlings were transplanted into the field at the beginning of May at the stage of 2nd-3rd true leaf using a technology for mid-season production of determinate and indeterminate tomatoes. The plants were grown in two watering regimes - optimum and 50% reduced. The reduced irrigation was applied 20 days after transplanting when the plants were well adapted in the field. The experiment was carried out in a randomized complete block design with two replications by 10 plants (area 2.4 m²). A micro-flow drip irrigation method was used with dripping wings and distributors giving 2 L h⁻¹, spaced 20 cm apart and placed along the row.

The following characters were recorded on two individual plants for each replication: productivity per plant (g) formed by all ripened fruits by 31 August, average fruit weight (g) and fruits per plant (number).

2.3. Climate parameters

Weather data were collected from June to August in 2016 and 2017 by weather station *Caipos Wave* (Caipos GmbH, Austria). Air minimum and maximum temperature (°C), air humidity (%), rainfalls (l/m²) and soil moisture at 15 and 30 cm depth (kPa) were recorded.

2.4. Statistical analysis

The results were given as means of eight independent (biological) replications. To compare differences among accessions grown in two watering regimes T-test and Duncan's multiple range tests were used. The decrease percentage (D%) was also calculated. Three-way analysis of variance were applied to show the effect of genotype, watering regime, productivity, productivity compounds and interaction between them (SPSS software).

3. RESULTS

3.1. Weather conditions

Significant differences in daily mean temperature between two studied years were not observed (Figure 1). The daily mean temperature for the period June-August over 25°C was measured in 54% and 51%

of days for 2016 and 2017 respectively. In the period of 2016 the daily mean temperature from June to August ranged between 19.78 and 28.80°C. Maximum temperature varied from 24.12 to 37.61°C. Temperature over 35°C was recorded in 26% of the days of the experimental period of 2016 with peaks of 37°C in the last decade of June and July. The data measured for 2017 showed that the daily mean temperature for the period June-August ranged between 17.10 and 32.02°C. The maximum temperature varied from 20.23 to 42.23°C. Temperature over 35°C was recorded in 40% of the days of the experimental period with peaks over 40°C in the last decade of June and the second decade of July.

Figure 1. Temperature values during the experimental period

During the first experimental year the total rainfalls were 134 l/m² more than the second one (76.5 l/m²) (Figure 2). The period of 2017 was characterized by lack of rainfalls in August except for 4.0 l/m² and 0.5 l/m² on 13th and 28th August respectively. The weather in June was also dry with only 19.5 l/m² total rainfalls. The rainfalls in 2016 were distributed as follows: June - 31.5 l/m², July - 38.0 l/m² and August - 64.5 l/m².

Figure 2. Rainfalls during the experimental period

3.2. Productivity characters

As a result of reduced irrigation and high temperatures a decrease in productivity based on the fruit number and fruit weight was observed. Among the studied determinate tomatoes for processing only BG 985 distinguished with slight reducing of productivity per plant less than 25% close to the positive control JAG 8810 (Table 1, Figure 3). A decrease of productivity per plant in other accessions of this group varied from 39.5% to 49.2%. The highest productivity per plant in water deficit was established in accession Venera. In the group of determinate tomato for fresh consumption the lowest decrease of productivity per plant was observed in accession BG Spectar (Table 2).

Table 1. Effect of high temperature and water deficit on the productivity and productivity parameters of determinate tomato accessions for processing

Accessions	Productivity per plant				Number of fruits per plant				Average fruit weight			
	50%	100%	D _{50%-100%}	D%	50%	100%	D _{50%-100%}	D%	50%	100%	D _{50%-100%}	D%
Kapri	929 ^d	1535 ^d	-606 ^{**}	39.5	21.5 ^c	29.8 ^{de}	-8.3 ^{**}	27.9	42.1 ^e	51.9 ^e	-9.8 [*]	18.9
Neven	1434 ^{cd}	2770 ^b	-1336 ^{***}	48.2	26.0 ^{bc}	38.8 ^c	-12.8 ^{**}	40.0	55.5 ^{bc}	71.9 ^{bc}	-16.4 ^{***}	22.8
Pautalia	1483 ^{cd}	2782 ^b	-1299 ^{***}	46.7	32.5 ^b	43.3 ^{bc}	-10.8 ^{**}	24.9	42.2 ^e	64.0 ^{cd}	-18.8 ^{***}	29.4
Venera	2035 ^b	4007 ^a	-1972 ^{***}	49.2	45.5 ^a	52.5 ^a	-7.0 [*]	13.3	46.5 ^{de}	76.0 ^{ab}	-29.5 ^{***}	38.8
BG 160	1249 ^{cd}	2227 ^c	-978 ^{***}	43.9	24.7 ^{bc}	45.3 ^b	-20.6 ^{***}	45.5	51.0 ^{cd}	49.4 ^e	1.6 ^{ns}	-3.2
BG 1527	1073 ^{cd}	1825 ^{cd}	-752 ^{**}	41.2	24.7 ^{bc}	30.0 ^{cd}	-5.3 [*]	17.7	43.5 ^{de}	61.0 ^d	-17.5 ^{***}	28.7
BG 2086	1562 ^{bcd}	2733 ^b	-1171 ^{***}	42.8	21.7 ^c	33.3 ^d	-11.6 ^{**}	34.8	72.6 ^a	82.3 ^a	-9.7 ^{***}	11.8
BG 985	1615 ^{bc}	2159 ^c	-544 [*]	25.2	22.8 ^{bc}	26.5 ^e	-3.7 ^{ns}	14.0	70.8 ^a	82.9 ^a	-12.1 ^{**}	14.6
JAG8810	2825 ^a	3287 ^{ab}	-462 [*]	14.1	46.5 ^a	47.5 ^b	-1.0 ^{ns}	2.1	64.4 ^b	69.2 ^c	-4.8 ^{ns}	6.9

a,b,c... - Duncan's Multiple Range ($p \leq 0.05$) Test; T – test $* \leq 0.05$, $** \leq 0.01$, $*** \leq 0.001$

The water deficit had a lower effect on the fruit weight. A slight increase of average fruit weight was recorded in determinate accession BG 160. A decrease of average fruit weight less than 15% was established in two determinate accessions for processing (BG 2086 and BG 985) and in one for fresh consumption (Solaris). In the other determinate accessions the reduction of average fruit weight ranged from 18.9% to 38.8% in the group of processing tomato and from 16.5% to 26.0% in tomato for fresh consumption (Table 1, 2).

Figure 3. Determinate tomato plants for processing grown under reduced irrigation (R) and optimum irrigation (O)

Reduced irrigation and high temperature significantly affect number of fruits per plant. In determinate tomato for processing only in accessions Venera and BG 985 the number of fruits per plant reduced with 13.3% and 14.0% respectively. The highest decrease in a number of fruits was registered in accession Neven (40.0%) (Table 1). In the group of determinate tomato for fresh consumption the loss of fruits was higher and varied from 23.9% to 48.7% depending of the genotype (Table 2, Figure 4).

Table 2. Effect of high temperature and water deficit on productivity and productivity parameters of determinate tomato accessions for fresh consumption

Accessions	Productivity per plant				Number of fruits per plant				Average fruit weight			
	50%	100%	D _{50%-100%}	D%	50%	100%	D _{50%-100%}	D%	50%	100%	D _{50%-100%}	D%
Marti	1759 ^b	3317 ^{ab}	-1558 ^{***}	47.0	20.0 ^{ns}	29.5 ^a	-9.5 ^{***}	32.2	88.1 ^b	110.4 ^b	-22.3 ^{**}	20.2
Milyana	1728 ^b	3392 ^{ab}	-1664 ^{***}	49.1	17.5 ^{ns}	28.7 ^a	-11.2 ^{***}	39.0	98.9 ^{ab}	118.4 ^{ab}	-19.5 ^{**}	16.5
Solaris	1734 ^b	3975 ^a	-2241 ^{**}	56.4	16.0 ^{ns}	31.2 ^a	-15.2 [*]	48.7	112.2 ^a	127.5 ^a	-15.3 ^{**}	12.0
Spektar	1925 ^a	2986 ^b	-1061 ^{**}	35.5	17.5 ^{ns}	23.0 ^b	-5.5 [*]	23.9	105.9 ^a	130.6 ^a	-24.7 ^{**}	18.9
BG 252	1601 ^b	3824 ^a	-2223 ^{***}	58.3	18.1 ^{ns}	32.5 ^a	-14.4 ^{***}	44.3	87.2 ^b	117.9 ^{ab}	-30.7 ^{***}	26.0

a,b,c...- Duncan's Multiple Range ($p \leq 0.05$) Test; T – test $* \leq 0.05$, $** \leq 0.01$, $*** \leq 0.001$

Figure 4. Determinate tomato plants for fresh consumption grown under reduced irrigation (R) and optimum irrigation (O)

The studied indeterminate tomato accessions demonstrated low heat tolerance with significant reduction of productivity and fruit weight under condition of 50% reduced irrigation (Table 3). Only one accession (BG 21 β) showed a decrease of productivity less than 50%. In the other indeterminate tomato accessions the decrease in productivity ranged from 54.3% to 75.7%. A reduction of 5.0% average fruit weight, the same as the positive control, was recorded in accession BG 2066. In two accessions (Plovdivska karotina and BG 735) the average fruit weight decreased less than 20%. In the other studied tomato accessions the average fruit weight decreased over 30%. A decrease of the fruits number by 22.3% was observed in accessions BG 21 β and by 32.3% in accession BG 720. In the other accessions the number of fruit per plant decreased significantly from 41.5 to 57.1% (Table 3, Figure 5).

Table 3. Effect of high temperature and water deficit on the productivity parameters of indeterminate tomato accessions

Accessions	Productivity per plant				Number of fruits per plant				Average fruit weight			
	50%	100%	D _{50%-100%}	D _%	50%	100%	D _{50%-100%}	D _%	50%	100%	D _{50%-100%}	D _%
Aleno sartse	927 ^{bc}	2787 ^{efg}	-1860 ^{***}	66.7	5.7 ^{cd}	11.7 ^d	-6.0 ^{***}	51.3	158.5 ^{bc}	240.3 ^d	-81.8 ^{***}	34.0
Ideal	1319 ^{ab}	3320 ^{cde}	-2001 ^{***}	60.3	10.7 ^b	18.3 ^b	-7.6 ^{***}	41.5	121.9 ^{bc}	182.8 ^e	-60.9 ^{**}	33.3
Pl. karotina	1015 ^{bc}	2248 ^{gh}	-1233 ^{***}	54.8	23.2 ^a	40.3 ^a	-17.1 ^{***}	42.3	45.1 ^d	55.6 ^f	-10.5 ^{ns}	18.9
Roz. sartse	1055 ^{bc}	3937 ^b	-2882 ^{***}	73.2	4.8 ^{cd}	11.2 ^d	-6.4 ^{***}	57.1	221.1 ^a	355.1 ^b	-134.0 ^{***}	37.7
BG 21 β	1353 ^a	2569 ^{fg}	-1216 ^{***}	47.3	12.2 ^b	15.7 ^c	-3.5 ^{**}	22.3	111.4 ^c	164.6 ^e	-53.2 [*]	32.3
BG 24/13	685 ^c	1920 ^h	-1235 ^{***}	64.3	24.2 ^a	42.2 ^a	-18.0 ^{**}	42.7	27.7 ^d	45.7 ^f	-18.0 ^{ns}	39.4
BG 720	1334 ^{ab}	4555 ^a	-3221 ^{***}	70.7	7.8 ^c	11.5 ^d	-3.7 ^{**}	32.3	169.1 ^b	401.1 ^a	-232.0 ^{***}	57.8
BG 735	1230 ^{ab}	3099 ^{def}	-1869 ^{***}	60.3	5.5 ^{cde}	10.8 ^d	-5.3 ^{***}	49.4	223.0 ^a	288.4 ^c	-65.4 ^{**}	22.7
BG 785	699 ^c	2880 ^{ef}	-2181 ^{***}	75.7	4.7 ^d	10.5 ^d	-5.8 ^{***}	55.2	150.4 ^{bc}	275.3 ^{cd}	-124.9 ^{***}	45.4
BG 822	1048 ^{bc}	3740 ^{bc}	-2692 ^{***}	72.0	7.7 ^{cd}	14.8 ^{cd}	-7.1 ^{***}	48.0	138.7 ^{bc}	251.4 ^{cd}	-112.7 ^{***}	44.8
BG 2066	1647 ^a	3605 ^{bcd}	-1958 ^{***}	54.3	6.1 ^{cd}	12.8 ^{de}	-6.7 ^{***}	52.3	272.8 ^a	287.0 ^c	-14.2 ^{ns}	5.0

a,b,c...- Duncan's Multiple Range ($p \leq 0.05$) Test; T – test $* \leq 0.05$, $** \leq 0.01$, $*** \leq 0.001$

Figure 5. Indeterminate tomato plants grown under reduced irrigation (R) and optimum irrigation (O)

The three-way analysis of variance showed that the watering regime mainly influenced (over 40%) the productivity per plant in the three studied tomato groups. The fruit number and average fruit weight per plant in determinate tomato for fresh consumption were affected by 60.52% and 39.20%, respectively.

Figure 6. Three-way analysis of variance and power of influence of genotype (factor A), year (factor B) and watering regime (factor C) In the group of determinate tomato for processing

Figure 7. Three-way analysis of variance and power of influence of genotype (factor A), year (factor B) and watering regime (factor C) In the group of determinate tomato for fresh consumption

Figure 8. Three-way analysis of variance and power of influence of genotype (factor A), year (factor B) and watering regime (factor C). In the group of indeterminate tomato for fresh consumption

The differences in number and average fruit weight per plant in determinate tomato for processing and indeterminate ones were determined by genotype. The effect of the year on the studied traits in three tomato groups was insignificant (Figure 6, 7, 8).

4. DISCUSSION

Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) is an important vegetable crop grown all over the world in different environmental conditions. Drought and heat stress become major limiting factors for the vegetative and reproductive development of the plants (Nahar & Ullah 2011). The yield is one of the traits that is strongly influenced by the environmental stress. Our results illustrated that the reduced irrigation and high temperatures led to a decrease in productivity per plant similarly to the data obtained by some authors (Patanè & Cosentino 2010; Zhang et al. 2017; Lovelli et al. 2017). In addition the level of the decrease of the yield was genetically dependent. The lowest reduction of the productivity under experimental conditions was established in accession BG 985 (25.2%) from the determinate tomato for processing and in accession Spectar (35.5%) from the determinate tomato for fresh consumption. The indeterminate tomato accessions showed higher sensitivity to the water stress reacting from 47.3% to 75.7% decrease of the productivity per plant. The results were very close to those reported by Sivakumar & Srividhya (2016) who observed that drought reduced yield from 30 to 80% in the studied eight tomato genotypes. Giuliani et al. (2018) also reported a different yield decrease in two tomato genotypes of 43% and 51% under water stress conditions. In both studies the authors assumed that the reduction of the yield less than 35-40% in some tomato genotypes might correspond to their somewhat tolerant nature toward drought stress.

Water deficit can reflect on the fruit weight. We observed that 50% reduced irrigation caused a reduction from 11.8% to 57.8%. Accessions BG 160, BG 2086, BG 985, Solaris and BG 2066 showed a slight reduction of average fruit weight. The results were consistent with those established by Sivakumar & Srividhya (2016) who found a decrease of average fruit weight less than 30% in the conditions of water deficit. Birhanu & Tilahun (2010) reported a decrease not only in the size but in the fruit number of plants subjected to drought stress. In our experiment the negative effect of water deficit on the fruit number was strongly expressed in the indeterminate accessions. A decrease over 40% was recorded in 9 of 11 studied indeterminate and in 4 determinate tomato accessions. The main reason for the change of the fruit amount is that drought stress during flowering stage reduces flower formation and increases flower shedding (Vijitha & Mahendran 2010).

Elevated temperature also significantly decreases the ability of tomato plants to set fruits (Foolad 2005; Srivastava et al. 2012). An increase of 2-4°C over the optimal temperature adversely affects on the physiological processes as pollen production and fertility, gamete development, flower abortion etc. and indirectly reduced yield (Peet, Wentworth & White 1998; Wahid et al. 2007). The recorded rise of maximum temperature up to 37-40°C in the last decade of June which was the period of fruit formation on the open field of Maritsa Institute probable additionally resulted in a decreased fruit number of the studied tomato accessions.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Screening and selection of tomato accessions under conditions of reduced irrigation and high temperature was performed in the current study. Considerable variation in productivity and productivity compounds among studied accessions was found. The results showed that the watering regime influenced mainly the productivity per plant in the three studied tomato groups, fruit number and average fruit weight per plant in determinate tomato for fresh consumption. Furthermore the number of fruits per plant was more strongly influenced by water deficit and might be used as an indicator for breeding of tolerant tomato genotypes. As a result, tomato accessions BG 985, Spectar and BG 21β were selected as tolerant to reduced irrigation and could be used as a base for the development of new varieties less sensitive to the environmental changes.

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